

Supplementary material

The following Table S1 and Table S2 list the parameter values tested for the two-population case, along with fitness values obtained. Due to space constraints, Table S1 shows the fitness scores of the estimated risks for the first reference population, while Table S2 shows the fitness scores of the risk for the second population.

<i>Parameters</i>									<i>Fit for estimated R1</i>		
<i>Range (R1)</i>	<i>Range (P1)</i>	<i>Partial sill (P1)</i>	<i>Nugget (P1)</i>	<i>Range (R2)</i>	<i>Range (P2)</i>	<i>Partial sill (P2)</i>	<i>Nugget (P2)</i>	ϵ_c	<i>Fit (naïve)</i>	<i>Fit (GWR)</i>	<i>Fit (Bayes)</i>
50.00	7.00	16500.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	180000.00	58000.00	15%	0.01	0.71	0.01
50.00	7.00	16500.00	2500.00	10.00	36.00	180000.00	58000.00	15%	0.01	0.71	0.01
50.00	7.00	16500.00	5000.00	10.00	36.00	180000.00	58000.00	15%	0.01	0.75	0.01
50.00	7.00	16500.00	10000.00	10.00	36.00	180000.00	58000.00	15%	0.00	0.79	0.01
75.00	7.00	16500.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	180000.00	58000.00	15%	0.01	0.67	0.01
25.00	7.00	16500.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	180000.00	58000.00	15%	0.01	0.69	0.01
10.00	7.00	16500.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	180000.00	58000.00	15%	0.01	0.64	0.01
5.00	7.00	16500.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	180000.00	58000.00	15%	0.01	0.49	0.01
50.00	3.50	16500.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	180000.00	58000.00	15%	0.01	0.74	0.01
50.00	14.00	16500.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	180000.00	58000.00	15%	0.01	0.57	0.03
50.00	28.00	16500.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	180000.00	58000.00	15%	0.08	0.49	0.11
50.00	56.00	16500.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	180000.00	58000.00	15%	0.11	0.46	0.16
50.00	7.00	10000.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	180000.00	58000.00	15%	0.01	0.68	0.01
50.00	7.00	20000.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	180000.00	58000.00	15%	0.01	0.71	0.01
50.00	7.00	40000.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	180000.00	58000.00	15%	0.01	0.65	0.01
50.00	7.00	80000.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	180000.00	58000.00	15%	0.02	0.57	0.02
50.00	7.00	16500.00	1250.00	5.00	36.00	180000.00	58000.00	15%	0.01	0.70	0.01
50.00	7.00	16500.00	1250.00	20.00	36.00	180000.00	58000.00	15%	0.01	0.74	0.02
50.00	7.00	16500.00	1250.00	40.00	36.00	180000.00	58000.00	15%	0.01	0.71	0.01
50.00	7.00	16500.00	1250.00	80.00	36.00	180000.00	58000.00	15%	0.01	0.72	0.02
50.00	7.00	16500.00	1250.00	10.00	18.00	180000.00	58000.00	15%	0.01	0.72	0.01
50.00	7.00	16500.00	1250.00	10.00	9.00	180000.00	58000.00	15%	0.01	0.68	0.01
50.00	7.00	16500.00	1250.00	10.00	4.50	180000.00	58000.00	15%	0.01	0.70	0.01
50.00	7.00	16500.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	90000.00	58000.00	15%	0.01	0.72	0.01
50.00	7.00	16500.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	45000.00	58000.00	15%	0.01	0.69	0.01
50.00	7.00	16500.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	22500.00	58000.00	15%	0.01	0.71	0.01
50.00	7.00	16500.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	36000.00	58000.00	15%	0.01	0.66	0.01
50.00	7.00	16500.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	180000.00	29000.00	15%	0.01	0.65	0.01
50.00	7.00	16500.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	180000.00	14500.00	15%	0.01	0.71	0.01
50.00	7.00	16500.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	180000.00	7250.00	15%	0.01	0.69	0.01
50.00	7.00	16500.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	180000.00	116000.00	15%	0.01	0.69	0.01
50.00	7.00	16500.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	180000.00	58000.00	5%	0.01	0.72	0.04
50.00	7.00	16500.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	180000.00	58000.00	10%	0.01	0.70	0.02
50.00	7.00	16500.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	180000.00	58000.00	50%	0.01	0.64	0.01
50.00	7.00	16500.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	180000.00	58000.00	100%	0.01	0.63	0.01

Table S1. Fitness scores for the estimated risk of the first reference population.

<i>Parameters</i>									<i>Fit for estimated R2</i>		
<i>Range (R1)</i>	<i>Range (P1)</i>	<i>Partial sill (P1)</i>	<i>Nugget (P1)</i>	<i>Range (R2)</i>	<i>Range (P2)</i>	<i>Partial sill (P2)</i>	<i>Nugget (P2)</i>	ϵ_c	<i>Fit (naïve)</i>	<i>Fit (GWR)</i>	<i>Fit (Bayes)</i>
50.00	7.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	10.00	36.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.01	0.26	0.02
50.00	7.00	16,500.00	2,500.00	10.00	36.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.01	0.30	0.01
50.00	7.00	16,500.00	5,000.00	10.00	36.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.01	0.29	0.02
50.00	7.00	16,500.00	10,000.00	10.00	36.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.01	0.30	0.01
75.00	7.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	10.00	36.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.01	0.30	0.01
25.00	7.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	10.00	36.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.01	0.23	0.01
10.00	7.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	10.00	36.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.01	0.18	0.01
5.00	7.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	10.00	36.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.01	0.15	0.01
50.00	3.50	16,500.00	1,250.00	10.00	36.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.01	0.27	0.01
50.00	14.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	10.00	36.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.01	0.28	0.01
50.00	28.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	10.00	36.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.01	0.30	0.01
50.00	56.00	16,500.00	1250.00	10.00	36.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.01	0.38	0.01
50.00	7.00	10,000.00	1,250.00	10.00	36.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.01	0.32	0.01
50.00	7.00	20,000.00	1,250.00	10.00	36.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.01	0.28	0.01
50.00	7.00	40,000.00	1,250.00	10.00	36.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.01	0.29	0.01
50.00	7.00	80,000.00	1,250.00	10.00	36.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.01	0.25	0.01
50.00	7.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	5.00	36.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.00	0.23	0.00
50.00	7.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	20.00	36.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.01	0.26	0.01
50.00	7.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	40.00	36.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.02	0.23	0.02
50.00	7.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	80.00	36.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.01	0.23	0.01
50.00	7.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	10.00	18.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.01	0.30	0.01
50.00	7.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	10.00	9.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.01	0.29	0.01
50.00	7.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	10.00	4.50	180,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.00	0.41	0.00
50.00	7.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	10.00	36.00	90,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.01	0.34	0.01
50.00	7.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	10.00	36.00	45,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.00	0.36	0.01
50.00	7.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	10.00	36.00	22,500.00	58,000.00	15%	0.01	0.43	0.01
50.00	7.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	10.00	36.00	360,000.00	58,000.00	15%	0.00	0.46	0.00
50.00	7.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	10.00	36.00	180,000.00	29,000.00	15%	0.01	0.23	0.01
50.00	7.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	10.00	36.00	180,000.00	14,500.00	15%	0.02	0.21	0.02
50.00	7.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	10.00	36.00	180,000.00	7,250.00	15%	0.02	0.11	0.03
50.00	7.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	10.00	36.00	180,000.00	116,000.00	15%	0.02	0.09	0.03
50.00	7.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	10.00	36.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	5%	0.01	0.42	0.01
50.00	7.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	10.00	36.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	10%	0.01	0.30	0.01
50.00	7.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	10.00	36.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	50%	0.01	0.28	0.01
50.00	7.00	16,500.00	1,250.00	10.00	36.00	180,000.00	58,000.00	100%	0.01	0.27	0.01

Table S2. Fitness scores for the estimated risk of the second reference population.